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revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D3.1 Methodological framework and guidelines for the comparative analysis

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
DoA	Description of the Action
WP	Work Package
MSF	Multiple Stream Framework

1. Introduction to the FIERCE project

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical, methodological and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors and their discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and main frames, and their impact on policy agenda and outcomes. These actors, and especially the feminist movement are researched through critical frame analysis, political ethnography and Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of labour market and migration; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; and gender-based violence. FIERCE covers eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE strives also to provide a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the ways in which debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics of agenda setting and policy processes. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organizations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive and innovative visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and “bottom-up” democratic strategies.

2. Introduction to WP3

Policy transformations and change arise from the complex interplay of actors, strategies, alliances, evolving societal and political conditions, and changing political agendas and priorities. Key questions in this context include: why certain policy issues and problem framings gain momentum, how they make it onto the political agenda, and the roles that various actors (including political leaders and entrepreneurs, civil society movements and advocates, and the media) play in these processes. Striving to understand which policy solutions are proposed, gain traction, and are accepted—or fail to be so—is central to the policy process and to the understanding of contemporary challenges to democracy and equality. In the context of FIERCE, where gender and gender policies are a focal point, it is particularly important to examine these factors, conditions and processes. Likewise, it is crucial to study the actors, their relationships and behaviors, since they contribute to decide whether specific issues become societal and policy priorities, or are excluded from the agendas, when not directly challenged and ostracized by decision-makers. In the case of the social movements, this includes considering whether they aim for political influence or refrain from engaging with the institutional arena, and why this happens. Some of these dynamics are already referred to in the plethora of studies recently published on anti-gender actors and their mobilizations (e.g. Kuhar and Paternotte 2017, Graff and Korolczuk 2020, Vida 2022, Butler 2024, Holvikivi, Holzberg & Ojeda 2024), on the democratic backlash, opposition to gender equality and de-democratization and the feminist movements’ responses. Yet the political processes, mechanisms and interactions regarding policy change within specific gender-sensitive areas and within different contexts have seldom been approached in a truly comparatively manner (across country contexts and policy areas). The WP3 main objectives, whose methodological guidelines and approach are outlined in this report (T3.1) are formulated against this background and research interest. Thus, our driving research question in WP3 is: *Which factors influence the inclusion or exclusion of gender-related issues on political agendas and shape the impact of feminist mobilizations across different contexts?*

2.1. Targeted Audience

The WP3 research results (D3.2 and D3.3) are addressed to and will be of interest for the wide audience, including academics in political science, gender studies, and public policy, as well as policymakers and government officials focusing on gender equality, LGBTQ+ rights and inclusive policymaking. Civil society organizations, feminist movements, and advocacy groups could also use the findings to help reflect and refine their strategies for standing up against the global challenges of the anti-gender movement (also in view of the US policy developments as described in the Project 2025) and promoting democratic innovations. Advocacy and lobby groups within the United Nations and the European Union may also find the insights valuable for completing their knowledge and advance gender-focused initiatives. Additionally, educators, trainers working on gender-sensitive issues, and journalists along with members of the general public and activists, could benefit from a deeper understanding of the dynamics of gendered policy processes and their impact on democratic participation. Our audience also includes the feminist network brought together throughout the FIERCE project's national and transnational labs, as detailed in T4.2 (Coordinating/facilitating co-creation sessions), T4.3 (Reporting on results) and T5.1 (Establishment of a transnational network bringing together feminist movements and public actors). This report (D3.1 - Methodological framework and guidelines for comparative analysis) provides a foundation for the FIERCE researchers to align on methodology and organization of the work ahead and present the theoretical framework to inspire and complete the work in D3.2 and D3.3.

2.2. Main Objectives and Description

The aim of WP3 is to build on the empirical data and published reports of WP1 and WP2, transitioning from the predominantly country-specific approach that has guided FIERCE project activities thus far to a comparative, multi-dimensional perspective focused on issue-driven problem and policy processes. Concretely, the research approach in WP3 transfers the focus from what defines and characterizes the country context background towards a focus on the broader key thematic areas and, next, across these dimensions. It is a two-step approach which strives to: 1) unpack the dynamics and developments characterizing the different policy contexts that influenced agenda setting, alliances, proposals, and decisions in relation to the specific gender policy issues; 2) identify new and unanticipated emerging issues, which need to be taken into account; 3) highlight overlapping gender policy issues and dynamics that may cut across the thematic dimensions.

To achieve its objectives, **WP3 aims to establish a methodological framework that identifies, selects and clusters core gender issues and dynamics across countries, enabling the identification of shared dimensions for analysis.** This framework will support a **cross-country comparative policy analysis of themes and subthemes**, initially within the project's identified five key thematic areas: labor market and migration, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, and gender-based violence. Our analysis focuses on the "policy windows" and on the conditions, similarities and differences that generated policy impact, or not, through a multi-stream policy lens (*see below, Section 4*). Additionally, it explores how issues, frames, and alliances align across policy fields, while uncovering opportunities for intersectional approaches. Furthermore, WP3 assesses the potential of feminist movements to foster democratic innovations by evaluating strategies and potential tools that can enhance recognition and inclusivity in policy decision-making processes (broadly understood).

2.3. Interconnections between WP1, WP2, WP4, WP5 and main Tasks

The tasks in WP3 are designed to build on the work conducted in WP1, WP2, WP4, and WP5 to achieve a comprehensive understanding of gender issues within a policy process framework. WP3 builds, therefore, on the rich pool of data gathered within the FIERCE project as well as reports, including: 1) Critical Frame Analyses for all countries (and summaries) applied to selected social movement documents and parliamentary debates; 2) Political Ethnography reports for each country (and

summaries) obtained through the pool of semi-structured interviews with representatives of groups and organizations, activists, advocates, and politicians; and 3) Discursive Network Analysis of gender/anti-gender debates, levels of controversies along with actors and their agree/disagree positioning.

Besides, WP3 also refers to the results and data available from the co-creative approach adopted in WP4, involving FIERCE Lab collaborations (nationally and transnationally) with feminist movements, civil society organizations and political actors. These activities allowed to foster practices of knowledge-sharing and to get information on strategies and alliances, democratic actions and initiatives at various levels to respond to main anti-gender and anti-feminist challenges within countries and at European/global level, as well as development of common tools, inclusive democratic solutions, networks of resilience, and policy recommendations. ns. Likewise, the FIERCE actions selected in WP4 (T4.4 FIERCE actions – Testing democratic innovation actions in partnership with local and national feminist movements) are expected to develop inclusive approaches to democratic governance and citizens' involvement in decision making processes. The FIERCE actions are analyzed by each country team, and they will provide empirical data for the analysis of feminist processes of democratic innovation and intersectional alternatives for inclusion, participation, and empowerment.

We envisage the WP3 activity to follow different preparatory and executive stages. **WP3 begins with a collaborative discussion in groups of the main gender issues from the country reports which warrant further analysis, integrating insights from the various WP data streams, while aligning them with the five key thematic areas.** This task is preparatory to the cross-country perspective and occurs at the team level to prompt discussions at thematic level.

The **next step entails a multi-level, cross-country comparative analysis within prefigured key thematic areas, focusing on the policy processes surrounding the most salient gender issues and debates.** This task (T3.1- Setting up the framework for the cross-country analysis, Leader AAU) aims to explain how specific gendered and feminist policy frames gained traction, or failed to do so, in the observed/researched period. It discusses how gender issues reached the political agenda, and whether they resulted in policy changes - or, conversely, why certain issues were excluded, silenced, or (deliberately) left unaddressed in policymaking. The **analysis draws theoretical and methodological inspiration from the Multi-Stream Framework** (e.g. Hill & Varone 2017, Zahariadis 2015, 2014, Króliczek 2013, Kingdon 1995) **Agenda Denial** (Cobb & Ross 1997) **Framing Theory, and the role of Emotions** (e.g. Maor 2024, Redlawsk 2006). The progression of cross-country comparative analyses (which will result in T3.2 – A Multidimensional and multi-level cross-country comparative analysis of key thematic areas, Leder MI) within each of the thematic group discussions will further help to refine and calibrate the use of this theoretical framework and background. Focus however remains on the policy processes, as outlined in the DoA under the WP descriptions.

Finally, specific **attention will be dedicated to a (cross-country) comparative analysis of feminist democratic innovations** (T3.3 – Cross-country comparative analysis of feminist innovations to rekindle democratic processes, Leader AAU) aimed at revitalizing democratic processes. This task aims to map and evaluate how feminist movements contribute to democratic innovations, assessing their strategies and tools to promote more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes, but also indicating the factors that might limit these efforts. In addition, we analyze intersectionality in practice by addressing the potential for inclusive policy making processes through the strengthening of intersectional feminist alliances and intersectional framings, as well as the challenges that this might entail, e.g., in terms of controversies within the feminist movements or political resistance against intersectional approaches. The findings will allow us to assess, e.g., whether opportunities for inclusion of intersectional framings and alliances are enhanced when themes cut across policy fields and institutional settings, thus potentially leaving more room for feminist influence and innovation.

By linking all these tasks (T3.1., T3.2, T3.3) under the WP3, we aim at systematically and fully unpack the dynamics of gendered policymaking (across countries and thematic areas), their intersections, and the potential for feminist-driven democratic transformation.

3. Step-by-step approach for the cross-cutting comparison within specific gender thematic working groups

To shift from a country-specific approach, where research is divided among national teams, to a cross-cutting that provides comparative insights into gender issues and their influence on debates and decision-making, we have implemented a step-by-step methodology guide. This approach aims to break away from entrenched research paradigms tied to national settings, which often persist due to their relative facility in coordination, labor division, and delivery within Horizon Europe projects involving several country teams.

The FIERCE project explicitly aims, as stated in the Grant Agreement, to overcome “methodological nationalism” in studies of feminist and anti-gender movements. WP3 prioritizes a “comparative approach to identify similarities and differences in how anti-feminist and feminist actors position themselves, influence policy, and drive societal change” (see DoA, Project 101061748 FIERCE, 2). This approach provides a broader understanding of the impact beyond national contexts and constraints.

The outlined steps address this concrete objective by actively challenging methodological nationalism also within the FIERCE consortium, recognizing that this shift does not happen spontaneously but requires deliberate effort and pushes. Moving beyond familiar national contexts, we argue, demands a conscious push to take researchers out of their “comfort zone” and foster a truly comparative perspective. This document is a practical roadmap to arrange this.

3.1. Step 1: The structuring of the gender thematic working groups

Identifying key gender thematic groups is an approach prefigures from the initial phases of the FIERCE project to better structure research and ensure the necessary policy field relevance (GA, Project 101061748 FIERCE, 8). The five key thematic areas introduced also purposely facilitate the comparative study across the eight countries, highlighting intersectional dynamics, and aligning findings with real-world challenges. Furthermore, this approach in WP3 allows to concretely assign researchers to dedicated groups and to organize the work division within the country teams in view of the cross-country gender thematic collaboration in the working groups. Research is thus organized within six main thematic groups, each focusing on a distinct gender related and policy relevant area: 1) Labour market, migration, and care work; 2) Health and reproductive rights; 3) LGBTQ+ rights; 4) Gender-based violence; 5) Democratic innovations (purposely introduced in view of D3.3); and 6) Intersectionality (explicit cross-cutting theme emerged during the project course). The working groups were initially formed based on the expressed interests of the teams, informed by their expertise in their respective cases and by their insight of the empirical data collection and initial analysis (at country level). The table below shows the current allocation of the teams of the leaders for each of the key thematic areas (see also GA, DoA at T3.2, 7).

Themes	Lead	Participants
Labour market, migration and care-work	UCM	SNS, UCM, UG, AAU
Health and reproductive rights	UG	AUTH, MIR, SNS, UCM, UG
LGBTQ+ rights	UL	AAU, KU, UL, SNS, UCM, UG
Gender based violence	SNS	AUTH, KU, SNS, UCM
Democratic Innovations	SV	AAU, EA, MIR, SV, KU, SNS
Cross-cutting intersectionality	MIR	AAU, EA, MIR, SNS, SV, UCM

Table 1: FIERCE thematic working groups

Each thematic group holds a *minimum* of one meeting before each plenary session (the FIERCE monthly consortium meetings) in the period from December 2024 and until June 2025. Group leaders will organize meetings, and we will discuss our findings and dilemmas at consortium meetings. Updates and main results from the thematic groups are to be discussed at the FIERCE plenary meetings. Other extraordinary meetings can be set up, if necessary, by the group leaders, task (T3.2) leader (MIR) and the Project Coordinator (Vilabs) and the WP3 leader and Scientific Coordinator (AAU).

An additional to the above and specifically dedicated group is also established with a focus on publication efforts and strategies. Participation in this group is voluntary, providing the opportunity to shape our publication strategy and streamline the FIERCE plans. The group includes members (both senior and early career scholars) of AAU, SNS, KU, MIR, and UL.

3.2. Step 2: Work within the thematic groups

The main task of the thematic groups is to identify the most relevant points of analysis to be carried out within their thematic area, based on the data collection of WP1 and WP2, and to produce one or several papers, using dimensions from the theoretical framework presented below to develop a comparative, multidimensional analysis. Each group decides which theoretical dimensions and empirical cases to include, focusing on throughout discussed relevance and saliency. The goal is to conduct analyses that make significant contribution to existing literature and provide new insights to the field. Groups are not required to address all theoretical dimensions or compare all country cases within the same theme.

Group leaders are responsible for: 1) scheduling the meetings and coordinating the main activities within their thematic group; 2) suggesting a rapporteur at each group meeting, who takes minutes of the main discussion points and of the agreed work to do; 3) uploading the group minutes, together with the relevant material in the group dedicated MS-Teams WP3 repository folder; and 4) coordinating the drafting and the work on the comparative collaborative papers to be submitted as part of D3.2 by the established deadlines (*see timeline below*).

Group participants need not meet up as a whole country team, but divide work amongst them, so that a country team member is represented at the relevant group meeting (*see table above*). This qualifies the team participant as main contributor and key recipient for the work on the specific theme, and co-writer in the finalization of the thematic groups' papers. Working groups provide feedback on each other's first drafts through an internal peer-review process, after which papers are exchanged and discussed among groups. Advisory Board members may also participate in the review process.

3.3. Timeline

The thematic working groups' activity officially starts in the beginning of December (M27). The period (M27-M29) is dedicated to discussing main issues within the groups and preparing a synopsis for the paper. Once the working group has decided on the main direction and focus of their paper (M29), the group leader registers these with the WP leader (AAU) to ensure an overview of which theoretical dimensions, empirical data, cases, etc. are being addressed across the thematic working groups. The first paper drafts are to be submitted by M31 and final version of the papers by M32. All papers are compiled to make up the final deliverable, with an overarching introduction to be developed by the task leader and the WP3 leader. For the papers we use the designated WP3-folders in the MS Teams repository to documents sharing. The working groups are also encouraged to present final versions of the papers at relevant international conferences (e.g., ECPR in Thessaloniki, 26-29 August 2025).

4. Theoretical and Methodological guidelines

4.1. Introduction

The multistream framework (MSF) is central to the research conducted in WP3, enabling a comprehensive analysis of gender issues by examining how problem frames, actors, relationships, strategies, and mobilization efforts influence agenda-setting and policy outcomes. This approach wants to move beyond state-centered, country-driven methods to adopt and privilege a comparative, dimension-driven perspective, focusing on the interactions of diverse policy entrepreneurs and the dynamics of inclusion or exclusion of gendered frames. By analyzing windows of opportunity, discursive shifts, the impact of crises, and shifting policy conditions and priorities, this framework highlights strategies that foster or hinder feminist influence on policy reforms and explores democratic innovations rooted in feminist practices.

4.2. A Multiple Stream Framework and Agenda Denial approach

The MSF, developed by John Kingdon (1984/1995), later refined by Nikolaos Zahariadis (2014), and employed by several others for the analysis of policy processes, provides the analytical lens to better understand the policy setting and policy making process. Policy process research can be referred to as “the study of the interactions over time between public policy and its surrounding actors, events, and contexts, as well as the policy or policies’ outcomes” (Weible 2014, 4). The MSF “explains how policies are made by government under conditions of ambiguity” (Zahariadis 2014, 25). The MSF model helps thus address the questions of “what determines the emergence of some ideas over others and investigates why certain ideas are used by government to formulate public policies and not others” (Ridde, 2009:940). MSF contributes to explaining how issues gain, but also fail to gain, traction on the political agenda. Key to this is considered the convergence of three main streams (Kingdon 1995, 19; Zahariadis 2014, 25): 1) the problem stream; 2) the policy/solution stream; and 3) the politics stream. Each is conceptualized as working separately from the others, driven by its own dynamics and rules. However, at critical points in time, or “policy windows”, conditions get ripe, and the three streams are coupled by policy entrepreneurs using a variety of strategies. The “coming together” of the streams also enhances the chances that policymakers will adopt a specific policy. However, in our approach we also take into account the fact that during the policy process certain issues are strategically **denied agenda access** through various tactics of **agenda denial** (Cobb and Ross 1997). These strategies can help clarifying why, although the circumstances are favorable for a policy to enter the agenda setting and decision-making, there might still be someone/something that works against the adoption of a policy or might affect its definition to the extent that the result is considered amputated, when not substantially changed by some of the actors promoting it. Below a more extended breakdown of the MSF framework is presented with some added considerations of agenda denial that will help the thematic groups to refer to the policy process. The theoretical framework is a parting, not a point of arrival for the comparative analyses that will result in D3.2. This approach allows comparisons to be guided by a policy process framework informed by the MSF without however being rigidly constrained by its specific methodological, or epistemological boundaries. For instance, comparative analyses may highlight certain aspects of the political process, such as agenda-setting, as particularly relevant for the comparative analysis of specific issues. The focus can then be on exploring the actors and factors that triggered policy developments, setbacks, or retrenchments in two or three countries, providing a more nuanced and targeted analysis.

4.2.1. Problem Stream

The problem stream involves the way in which a problem is defined and the conflicts that arise over its interpretation by different actors involved. Various stakeholders have different perceptions of the problem, resulting in debates over its significance, urgency and resolution. Problems can surface to the

policy agenda through indicators (for instance, growing number of feminicides or attacks against transpersons), focusing events (e.g., the Gender quota bill approved by the Polish government in 2011, the #MeToo movement in 2017, the overturn of the Roe vs. Wade in the US in June 2022, the Murder of Giulia Cecchettin by her former boyfriend in 2023, or the Women's Strike on the International Women's Day in 2018) or feedback mechanisms (reports emphasizing the fail to reach gender equal pay and representation). It is thus important to try to identify what the triggers were that contributed bringing a gender issue on the political agenda in the different contexts (see policy windows below). However, it is also important within this context to consider how (policy) problems are differently formulated and understood by the different actors and where we can see that levels of controversy/disagreement are highest. At this level some problem formulations can also be denied access to the public policy agenda. This can for instance happen through low-cost strategies, i.e. ways that avoid "to expend resources that are unnecessary to fend off the initiating group" involving "little money, few people, and minimal time" (see Cobb & Ross 1997, 27). The key element is non-confrontation such as the non-recognition **of the problem**, or the outright **denial that the problem exists as described**, or the **refusal to acknowledge the groups** that are pushing for a specific issue. By discrediting or downplaying the issue, some policy actors can prevent it from being seen as a pressing concern and something that needs policy action.

4.2.2. Policy Stream

Within the MSF approach the policy/solution stream is referred to as the collection of ideas, proposals, and potential solutions circulating within different policy communities and groups. Some of these ideas end up gaining traction and support, while others do not. How and why does this happen when we concretely look at the gender issues analyzed through the lens of the key thematic areas? The viability of ideas can be determined by several factors such as: technical feasibility, value acceptability, resource availability, path-dependency, etc. In cases of agenda denial, **medium-cost strategies** can come into play (Cobb & Ross 1997: 29-38), such as questioning the ethics, morals or behavior of the leaders and entrepreneurs suggesting specific proposals and potential solutions or linking the proposed solution with groups portrayed as unpopular, or radical (for instance in the case of the demands put forward by feminist groups). A more aggressive denial approach may involve the **reversal of roles**, where opponents claim **victim status**, or release **false information** to discredit the solution being proposed by some groups.

4.2.3. Politics Stream

The politics stream of the MSF approach addresses the broader institutional and cultural/value context in which policymaking occurs. Factors such as public mood, political pressure from interest groups, party ideology, changes in government, etc. can all influence this stream. Here, agenda denial can manifest through **symbolic placation – medium-cost strategy** where the appearance of addressing an issue is created without substantial action. By invoking **community norms, morals, or loyalty**, policymakers can superficially address concerns without allowing the problem to truly gain traction on the agenda and approve solutions which are not satisfactory.

4.3. Multiple Stream Framework: Key Concepts

4.3.1. Policy Window

This is the critical moment when conditions get favorable for agenda-setting or decision-making. The window opens when problems (for reasons that need to be identified and made explicit) are considered urgent, and viable solutions are available, but it only stays open for a limited time. If the coupling between streams does not happen quickly within this period, the window closes. It is therefore important to track what happens when a policy window opens (e.g., with #MeToo for a discussion of consent-based rape legislation, or the decision of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal to rule that

abortions due to fetal defects were unconstitutional, or the Supreme Court decision in the US to overturn *Roe v. Wade* for pro-choice mobilizations). In terms of agenda denial, **high-cost strategies** (Cobb & Ross 1997, 38-41) might be employed to **withhold electoral support** or even resort to **legal threats**, such as **lawsuits or sanctions**, to ensure certain issues are kept off the table, particularly during this sensitive window of opportunity.

4.3.2. Policy Entrepreneurs

Policy entrepreneurs are to be understood as groups, organizations, individuals, who advocate for specific policy ideas, or proposals (Kingdon 1995, 225). These people may be politicians, civil servants, pressure group leaders, or civil society organizations with issues they want to put on the public agenda. They are, according to Kingdon, like ‘surfers waiting for the big wave’ (Kingdon, 1995, p. 225), on the look-out for a combination of public concern about a problem and political interest in doing something about it. They invest their time, resources, and political capital in pushing for solutions at different levels, sometimes privileging for instance the local or transnational level to the national. The motivations behind their advocacy can vary and include personal beliefs and commitment, patterns of political socialization, but also political ambitions, financial incentives, etc. However, policy entrepreneurs might also face resistance through agenda denial strategies, where their efforts are undermined by **raising fears** about **high complexity** or potential **negative spillover effects** of their proposals. By highlighting these concerns, political actors can delay or completely block the entrepreneur’s push for policy change. The broad definition of policy entrepreneurs encompasses diverse actors beyond traditional political elites, emphasizing their active role in identifying windows of opportunity and advocating for solutions. The term entrepreneurs allows to integrate civil society organizations as key players in the public debate and policy making process (unlike the tendency in classic policy analysis to restrict the field to more narrowly defined institutional actors). This approach creates a more inclusive policy framework to work with, although one must pay attention to the risk of diluting differences and specificity among the actors involved, for instance in terms of economic and political power.

4.3.3. Stream Coupling and Timing

MSF highlights the importance of **coupling** between the streams. When the three streams (problem, policy, politics) align, it creates a window of opportunity for significant policy change. In this sense, opportunities for agenda setting come and go with shifting attention to issues, influenced, e.g., by the short attention span of the media and the changing needs of politicians in the course of an electoral cycle. The stream convergence usually occurs during periods of political change, or when a problem becomes particularly pressing, e.g., due to triggering events. However, if one of the streams is missing (e.g., no viable solution is available), then the issue remains off the decision agenda. This emphasizes the “fleeting” nature of policy windows. Kingdon observes: “If a solution is not available, a problem cannot be found or is not sufficiently compelling, and support is not forthcoming from the political stream, then the subject’s place on the decision agenda is fleeting. The window may be open for a short time, but if the coupling is not made quickly, the window closes.” These observations remind of the work of Antony Downs on the media attention cycle in politics (Downs 1972) but need to be addressed also concretely and empirically through cross-country cases and across different thematic areas to find explanations.

The MSF also identifies the role of the spill-over/path dependency effect, that is, the impact of one policy change on other policies. Yet, although the approach considers the effects of **incrementalism** it critically approaches this by considering the dynamic way in which the streams join and policy windows open. The interest in this sense is placed on the way in which key actors/policy entrepreneurs both inside and outside government operate and whose proposals and actions eventually “come together”. Or as Nikolaos Zahariadis argues: “Collective choice is not merely the derivative of individual efforts

aggregated in some fashion but rather the combined result of structural forces and cognitive and affective processes that are highly context dependent” (Zahariadis in Sabatier and Weible 2014, 26).

Agenda denial adds another layer to this dynamic by introducing tactics/strategies that try to prevent the coupling to take place in the first place, either by **discrediting** the problem and/or the groups, organizations and individuals who propose them, or by complicating the proposed solution, making it less politically viable.

4.4. Strategic Framing: Mobilizing Action, Shaping Policy

Frames have both cognitive and strategic roles, and they help shaping the way social problems, events, and policies are understood and acted upon. Cognitively, they interpret and define reality (e.g. Lakoff 2004), while strategically (Benford and Snow, 2000) they are crafted to motivate action and achieve goals. In social movement literature, frames are viewed as “conscious strategic efforts” to create shared understandings that legitimize and drive collective action (McAdam et al., 1996). By linking issues to individual experiences or marginalized groups, frames mobilize target groups and allies, inspiring and justifying campaigns (Caiani and della Porta, 2011). Similarly, the **strategic potential of frames is emphasized in policy analysis** as the “conscious shaping [by social and political actors] of political demands to negotiate desired political outcomes” (Bacchi, 2005: 204). Thus, the strategic use of frames relates to the ways in which they are used by political and civil society actors to (re)negotiate meaning in claims-making and political struggles in public debate or policy-making processes, within or outside the formal institutional framework. In other words, strategic framing is used when actors take stock of the political context, or the public debate and shape their ideas and demands accordingly to enhance their chances to exert influence and achieve change in the wished direction. In a gendered perspective, strategic framing is emphasized in relation to (de)gendering, or the (deliberate lack of) articulation of intersectionality, as a strategic tool, for instance when feminist movements in their efforts to gain institutional support for their demands, articulate liberal frames to seek broader resonance – or, on the contrary, refrain from interacting with institutional politics but rather emphasize intersectional feminist framings and alliances to make an impact on public debate.

Master frames not only shape how particular social issues are discussed but also influence what gets included or excluded from the political agenda. Through **agenda denial** tactics, anti-gender actors can strive to block progressive gender reforms by framing them as culturally illegitimate, inappropriate, irrelevant. By consistently linking gender with threats to specific societal and cultural values, these actors shift the focus from actual policy debates to **symbolic battles** over cultural identity, values, morality.

This framing process reflects the dynamics seen in other contentious social issues, where competing groups use **alternative cultural images** to steer the public discourse. For example, in the abortion debate, the “pro-life” framing emphasizes the moral sanctity of unborn children, while “pro-choice” advocates focus on bodily autonomy and women’s rights. These competing frames are underpinned by **deeply held cultural values**, and their success in shaping the public agenda depends on which ‘worldview’ gains more resonance with the broader public.

Framing strategies, when deployed through consistent master frames like “gender ideology” are pivotal in shaping both the substance and direction of social and political debates. By drawing on culturally resonant symbols, language, and emotions, anti-gender actors can maintain **ideological continuity** and **consistency**, while influencing public perception and political decision-making across various domains. If in power or holding influential positions, these master frames can be used as strategies of agenda denial that can resonate with a public opinion that has been exposed to these representations of the problem.

4.5. Role of Emotions in the Multiple Streams Framework

Traditional applications of the MSF often overlook the critical role that emotions play in shaping the policy process, including how emotions influence the actions of the policy entrepreneurs and policy decision-makers. While the MSF does acknowledge emotions to some extent through the concept of “public mood”, a key factor in the political stream, described as the “prevailing climate of opinion” (Zahariadis, 2015, p. 468), this emotional dimension remains underexplored. Recent literature, however, is increasingly addressing this gap by introducing emotions right into the MSF. Scholars like Maor (2024) emphasize the need to apply an emotional lens to better understand how emotions interact with the policy problem, policy, and politics stream in shaping policy agendas and eventually outcome. Sociologist Arlie Russell Hochschild (2024, 2016) in her recent books explores the role of emotions in politics primarily through her concept of “emotional labor” and her research into the “deep stories” that shape people's political views. Her work emphasizes that emotions are central to political behavior, identity, and decision-making. Emotions play a crucial role in shaping how individuals, for example, connect with political movements, or (‘charismatic’) leaders. Politicians often try to evoke emotions like hope, anger, or fear to build support, avoiding shame and guilt (Widmann 2021). By incorporating emotions into the framework, it becomes possible to develop more nuanced hypotheses about how emotions also inform agenda-setting, influence policy decision-making, and contribute to the creation of “protective” policy outcomes.

Incorporating emotions helps explain why certain issues gain traction, or why policy windows open at specific moments—public mood is not just a rational calculation, but also shaped by collective emotional responses, such as fear, outrage, or hope. This broader emotional perspective offers deeper insights into how policy entrepreneurs not only rely on technical expertise or political resources but also leverage emotions to push their agenda forward. In turn, emotions can influence whether a policy solution is embraced or rejected within the political landscape, particularly in the case when there are several policy alternatives, and the timeframe is narrow.

5. Conclusions

Policymaking is often a complex, non-linear process where multiple factors and actors must align for policy change to occur. It often reveals the main controversies and conflict among actors, as well as the alliances and strategies activated. By understanding how problems, solutions, and politics interact, civil society and policy actors can better grasp when and how policy windows open and learn how to take advantage of the situation to influence the agenda-setting process. Equally important it is to understand agenda denial strategies, which can explain why some issues fail to gain traction, even in the presence of favorable conditions and policy entrepreneurs.

Understanding the mechanisms of policy process and how to position themselves in it can be particularly valuable for feminist and LGBTQ+ movements and politicians. It can help unwrap the complexities of the policy making process and seize opportunities to bring gender-related issues to the forefront, while trying to counteract opposition tactics that aim at disempower the gender equality agenda. By understanding the strategic use of framing, the mechanisms behind agenda denial and the role played by emotions, feminist advocates can craft more efficient campaigns and policy claims, also drawing maximal benefit from policy opportunity windows by building transversal alliances that can ensure gender and equality remain priority in public discourse and policy making.

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